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ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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Fade-Painted Refuge

Cradled by the hills and mountains – creeks in between,
There stood an old-fashioned, faded building.
Painted in off-white, yellow, and green,
Surrounded by trees, nipa huts, and corn fields.

It may be old, small, and far,
But for Aboy – it's where his future is about to unfold.
Conquering the distance and struggles along the way,
Braving the storms and overflowing rivers on rainy days.

Reaching the grounds before sunrise is his goal,
Had to endure long walks on an empty stomach.
Passing through narrow roads – etched by footsteps,
Of poverty, dreams, and responsibilities.

People would call it school – a place for learning,
Fun, plays, values, and discipline.
But for him, it is an escape plan – a refuge,
From everything that weighs heavier than he holds.

Aboy is the youngest in a family of six,
Mom passed away at three – life is hard.
Life is everything in corn fields – every corn bit,
Work and school had to be juggled.

Driven by poverty and responsibilities,
He had finished school for himself and his family.
Now, taking still the same narrow path
In a complete uniform, with books and a laptop bag.

That fade-painted refuge stands still
Amidst the storm and the rain, the years passed.
The same old and small – a far base,
Yet full of dreams fulfilled, including his.